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A Variable-Length Chromosome Genetic Algorithm to Solve a Road Traffic Coordination Multipath Problem

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ABSTRACT The problems related to traffic coordination in intersections are quite common in large cities. Current solutions are based on the utilization of static priorities (i.e. yield signs), on variable signaling like traffic lights, or even on the physical modification of the road structures by transforming intersections in roundabouts. The emergence, evolution, and consolidation of technologies that enable the paradigm of connected and autonomous vehicles have allowed the development of new solutions where the vehicles' coordination follow a preset path without stopping when entering the intersections. In this work, we propose using a genetic algorithm with variable-length chromosomes to solve the vehicle coordination multipath problem in intersections. The proposed algorithm is focused on optimizing the vehicles' arrival sequencing according to preset flow rates. While other solutions assume the same flow rates in every branch of the intersection, in our proposal the traffic flows can be asymmetric. We extend one of the existent intersection models, based on fixed paths, to allow multiple paths. This means that each vehicle can go from any input point to any output branch in the intersection. Moreover, we have designed specific selection, crossover and mutation operators, and a new methodology to carry out the crossover function between different sized individuals, which are adapted to the specific peculiarities of the problem. Our proposal has been validated by carrying out tests using input data with known solutions and with random data. The results have been compared with systems based on other optimizers, obtaining improved results in the fitness outcome up to 9.1%, and up to 126% in computation time.

INDEX TERMS Cooperative systems, genetic algorithms, intelligent vehicles, road traffic intersection, optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

In road traffic systems, a particular problem in terms of security and efficiency is to achieve the coordination of vehicles in intersections, roundabouts, and ramps [1]. In the United States, over 40% of the almost 6 million accidents produced over a year are intersection-related crashes [2]. This is due to the fact that intersections are a natural path confluence zone, and therefore, are prone to collisions. The evolution of the technologies used in Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) has allowed an increment on the generation and exchange of

information between vehicles (V2V), and between vehicles and the infrastructure (V2I). In the same way, new paradigms such as Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs), are expected to experiment a huge expansion in the following years. In the year 2030, about 98% of vehicles are expected to be connected, due to the decreasing prices of the related technology and a favorable legislation [3]. These technologies are being applied to reduce the accidents in confluence zones through the improvement in traffic coordination techniques.

This work is focused on obtaining synchronized vehicle sequences according to desired preset traffic flows. This optimization process must guarantee a safe crossing while

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complying with the destination preferences (that is, their turn selection) of each vehicle.

According to the available literature, there are multiple works related to the vehicles' coordination techniques [4]. For instance, the vehicle decision-making process about choosing to cross or to give way to an oncoming vehicle is studied in works as [5]. Also, in [6] the authors apply game theory techniques over "Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control" equipped vehicles to solve this problem. It is possible to classify the works related to the vehicles' coordination in intersections in those which perform a study of the vehicle coordination in a single intersection [7], [8], and those focused on the coordination of two or more intersections [9]–[11]. Another classification criterion could divide them into systems for the management of intersections using fixed or variable traffic signaling [12], and systems which opt to variate the arrival times of vehicles to the conflict zones, without using any visible signaling [13]. Traffic lights based on constant time cycles, along with the yield signs, have been the most common way of managing intersections. Nowadays, and partially because of the emergence of vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication systems [14], other dynamic programming schemes for traffic lights are possible. The use of fuzzy logic traffic light systems considering the traffic levels in each input point of an intersection has been found useful in [15] applied to a specific use case in Kuwait city. Other fuzzy logic controllers working in cooperation with Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) can be found in [16] which analyze possible turns of vehicles and manage green time and cycle change of traffic lights. Although these works improve traffic light programming for the management of isolated intersections, some vehicles still must wait to access them.

From the point of view of possible heuristic search systems which could be used to solve the vehicle coordination problems, Genetic Algorithms (GA) have been extensively used and have provided good results. Following a traditional focus on traffic lights management, in [17] the authors propose a GA-based architecture, traffic micro-simulations and cluster computing mechanisms for the adjustment of traffic lights phases in a city. The proposed system is effective in reducing the waiting times of vehicles. Specifically, there are solutions that manage the vehicle crossing at an intersection by calculating an orderly sequence of arrivals, where each vehicle follows a specific path that avoids collisions without the need to alter their speed when they enter the intersection. We refer to these arrival sequences as patterns in this work. In [18] the authors propose an intersection hybrid management system where, when an emergency vehicle is close to the intersection, a GA calculates efficient sequences to prioritize this type of vehicle. The rest of the time, the system uses a conventional management system depending on the vehicle's trajectories. In a similar way, [19] uses a GA to obtain optimal vehicle sequences. Vehicle speed varies based on these sequences, allowing the vehicles to cross the intersections without stopping. These works behave in a reactive way depending on the

network conditions. In [20], instead, the research focuses on generating the incoming vehicle sequences (or patterns) that maximize resource utilization in the intersection. If vehicles in the network adapt themselves to these optimal patterns, the global efficiency of the system may be increased. Taking these previous works into account, we have chosen to use a genetic algorithm as the basis of the proposed optimization process.

Regarding the codification of the problem, the works referenced in the previous paragraphs that rely on a GA use fixed-length individuals. However, this has the drawback that the pattern length that allows an optimal solution to the optimization problem is not known *a priori*. Because of that, if we want to obtain the optimal arrival sequences of vehicles at an intersection, we must initiate several optimization processes. Harvey studies in [21] the possible techniques which could be applied to crossover operators in GA where variable-length genotypes (VLGs) are used. That work is focused mainly on how the crossover points should be selected to guarantee that the parents' genotypes represent the same type of information. He proposes using a recombination operator able to, given a crossover point in the primary genotype, choose a complementary crossover point in the other parent. For a different domain, in [22], the authors review the existing solutions using variable-length genomes and the effects of this codification in the algorithm convergence. Another example of this type of genomes applied to event planning can be found in [23], where the solution of a problem can be obtained applying a variable number of steps. Focusing on traffic-related problems we find examples such as [24], where Qiongbing and Lixin use a GA with variable-length chromosomes to solve path optimization problems. Each gene of the chromosome represents a point in the traffic network, and a set of genes determine a path. In this case, the authors improve the crossover operator that can be used in this kind of scenarios. The previously referenced methods for variable-length genotype crossover can be summarized in three main concepts: optimal selection of crossover points (in different-size genotypes, which points refer to the same type of information), crossover process (how to generate a new individual and update its genotype after the process), and the addition or removal of independent value genes (for instance, adding an extra step in a process or adding a new node in a path).

Every intersection may have a different shape and restrictions. In our previous work on intersection management [20], based on fixed paths between input and output points, we showed that the diversity in geometrical shape and usage patterns in real-world intersections pose a challenge for optimization and that careful modeling is critical for optimization to succeed. In this work, we generalize this approach which allows us to use one single optimization process to reach an optimal or suboptimal solution, independently of the vehicle paths and rates that are desired to be managed by the intersection, and of the pattern size needed to achieve those goals. Consequently, in this paper, we extend the

Optimized Crossing Patterns (OCP) system by removing the turn restrictions and allowing to go from any input point to any output branch in the intersection. Moreover, to improve the algorithm performance, we have modeled the problem using a variable-length genotype Genetic Algorithm. This system allows obtaining the optimal vehicles' arrival sequencing according to preset flow rates along with the shortest pattern length in a single optimization process. Our contributions to this field are the following:

- We have extended our previous intersection model (OCP) by adding the possibility for each vehicle to go freely from any input point to any output branch. We have named this new version Optimized Crossing Patterns with Multiple Paths (OCP-MP). This allows expanding the search space, and therefore potentially improve the system performance.
- We have proposed an optimizer based on a variable-length chromosomes GA that allows obtaining the optimal arrival sequences of vehicles in a single execution (Optimized Crossing Patterns with Multiple Paths and Variable Length or OCP-MP-VL).
- We have defined a custom method to perform the crossover process between individuals of different lengths based on the contraction and expansion of chromosome genes adapted to our problem.
- We have proposed a new methodology for the generation of initial populations and custom crossover and mutation operators adapted to our particular problem.
- Our proposal has been validated using data with a known solution and random data. The results have been compared with the results obtained using other optimizers.

The rest of this paper has been organized in the following way. In section II we show the fundamental elements of the microscopic simulator used in this work and the OCP system [20] which is used as the base for our proposal. In section III we describe the proposed solution for solving the traffic coordination problem. In that section, we define the improvements adopted over the OCP model and the new methodology to obtain the best vehicle arrival rate using a GA (the initial population generation mechanism, and the selection, mutation and crossover operators designed to use variable-length chromosomes). Moreover, we define the fitness function which results will be the value to minimize by the proposed GA. After that, we define the set of experiments for the validation of the proposal by comparing it to other optimization methods for the same problem (Section IV). We discuss these results in Section V. Finally, we explain our conclusions and future work lines (Section VI).

II. BACKGROUND

In this section, we briefly describe the microscopic simulator based on Traffic Cellular Automata (TCA) and the OCP method we proposed in [20], which will be used as the basis for this work.

FIGURE 1. Diagram of the basic behavior of the microscopic simulator based on a Traffic Cellular Automata (TCA).

The modeling process for a cellular automata which aims to simulate the behavior of vehicles crossing an intersection is divided into two phases: the modeling of the intersection and the behavior of the simulator itself. In the modeling phase, the geographic space is divided using a two-dimension grid. Depending on the specific shape of the intersection, the size of each division will be different. The movements available for vehicles are modeled following the von Neumann model, which means that they can continue from one cell to any one of the 4 adjacent cells. Each cell stores the specific turn restrictions applied in each case, so it is possible that some of the movements are restricted in some cells. In each simulation step, the vehicles can advance just one cell, and the total simulation time will be dependent on the size of the pattern to simulate and the size of the maximum route in the system. The implemented simulator can store the cells' occupation in each simulation step, being able to return metrics about minimum occupation, maximum occupation and average occupation in the intersection, turn flows from each branch, and the minimum, maximum and average collisions. A collision is detected when 2 or more vehicles use the same cell in the same simulation step. The process for moving two vehicles and the collision detection processes are shown in Figure 1.

The optimization problem raised in [20] had as a goal the generation of the maximum possible intersection utilization. To achieve this goal, it used a fitness function based on the maximum average occupation of the intersection during the simulation time. The OCP methodology includes the intersection modeling process and a labeling system for each element of the model, the calculation of the paths from input to output points in the intersection, and the optimizer based on a genetic

algorithm which obtains the ideal crossing patterns. OCP uses the vehicle position in a specific lane to determine its route. This method facilitates the algorithm convergence and simplifies the problem codification but introduces a restriction in the maximum traffic flow that can be directed to a specific output. OCP has three main limitations: The first one is that vehicle routes are limited by their position in the input lanes of the intersection. The second one is that the optimization process must be executed for each pattern length, so it is necessary to repeat the GA for each pattern length to test. Finally, OCP is focused on obtaining the maximum average occupancy of the intersection, regardless of desired traffic flow rates.

III. PROPOSED GENETIC ALGORITHM WITH AUTOMATED CHROMOSOME LENGTH EXPANSION AND CONTRACTION

A. PROBLEM FORMULATION

We model the problem of traffic coordination in road intersections in a similar way as [1], [11]. Accordingly, we define Γ_i as the space occupied by a vehicle when following a path between two points in the traffic network depending on the vehicle size. Given two or more vehicles, if there exists a non-null zone such that $\Gamma_c = \Gamma_1 \cap \Gamma_2 \cap \dots \cap \Gamma_n$, Γ_c represents a critical region in the traffic network, where it is possible that collisions between vehicles are produced. Once the Γ_i paths which can generate critical regions (affecting the safety constraints of the problem) are established, the cost for each vehicle is denoted by $J_i(x_i(t), u_i(t)) = \int_0^{+\infty} \Lambda_i(x_i(t), u_i(t), t) dt$ where x_i and u_i are the state and input/control vectors, respectively, and the stage cost $\Lambda_i(x_i(t), u_i(t), t) dt$ varies depending on the parameter to optimize (instantaneous power consumption, deviation from a target speed, etc.). Using this formulation, the N-vehicle optimal coordination problem can be treated as a constrained optimal control problem where the goal is to minimize $\sum_{i=1}^N J_i(x_i(t), u_i(t))$. In our case, we need to solve the problem as a combinatorial problem with constraints which grows exponentially depending on the path options and pattern length, or features of the intersection such as its number of branches, lanes per branch and its shape. That is, any variation of these parameters can change the number of critical regions Γ_c , modifying the complexity of the problem. An example of convergence and complexity results of a similar problem is shown in [25]. In our research work, the vehicle dynamics and the associated metrics described mathematically in the previous lines (route times, intersection occupation, collisions, etc.) are managed by the cellular automata intersection simulator shown in section II.

In the following, we define the proposed methods and techniques to obtain the best vehicle patterns according to their turn preferences. The resulting patterns induce vehicle arrival rates which enable safe crossings at the intersection while respecting destination preferences.

B. PROBLEM ENCODING

The method we proposed in [20], which defines the OCP system, allows the univocal identification of each element in an intersection. OCP encodes the presence or absence of vehi-

FIGURE 2. Labeling of the elements of an intersection of 4 branches and 3 lanes per branch.

cles in the patterns as a binary value, obtaining a fixed-length chromosome composed of a bit string. The codification of each GA individual is carried out by using a bit string where 1 represents the presence of a vehicle and 0 its absence. The paths of the vehicles in the intersection are fixed by their access lane. The input and output points are labeled with the tags i_{BL} and o_{BL} , respectively. The trajectories or routes followed by the vehicles inside of the intersection are denoted by the possible routes between each i_{BL} and each o_{BL} . These routes must comply with the turn restrictions (T_v), which represent the movement options from each cell to its adjacent cells. In [20], the routes of the vehicles were determined by the input lane used by the vehicle when accessing the intersection, so the maximum flows for a given turn option were determined by the capacity of the correspondent lane.

In this work, we propose an extended optimization algorithm based on OCP, where, in contrast, the vehicles can use different paths at the intersection even if they use the same entry point (OCP-MP). In addition, we use a GA based on chromosomes with variable-length (OCP-MP-VL) to obtain the optimal pattern length in a single optimization process. In OCP-MP, an intersection is composed of a given number of branches or arms. Each branch is also divided into input and output lanes. Along this section, for easier comprehension of the proposed operators and algorithms, we use an intersection composed of 4 branches with 3 input lanes and 3 output lanes in each branch. The main elements of this intersection are shown in Figure 2.

The elements of the intersection are denoted as follows:

$$B(x) \mid x = \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (1)$$

$$L_{B(x)}(y) \mid y = \{1, 2, \dots, m\} \quad (2)$$

FIGURE 3. Paths with a single turn option from all input points of a specific branch. a) Paths from i_{11} . b) Paths from i_{12} . c) Paths from i_{13} .

where x is a set of integer numbers from 1 to n , being n the total number of branches in the intersection. In the same way, y is a set of integer numbers from 1 to m which identifies the m input lanes from the branch $B(x)$. Only the input lanes must be identified, given that the output lanes do not intervene in the problem formulation.

Each input lane is divided into virtual cells, as shown in Figure 2. These cells represent the position of a single vehicle in the platoon accessing the intersection. The cell's size is fixed and has been selected to ensure enough separation between vehicles for them to maneuver in the intersection. That is, the position of a vehicle in a specific virtual cell determines both the access point to the intersection (denoted by i_{BL}) and the instant for this access. Every vehicle at the same distance in cells from the intersection will access it at the same time instant.

The values associated with each virtual cell of the platoons indicate the route or trajectory which each vehicle will follow in the intersection. Equation (3) defines these values.

$$P_{L_{B(x)}(y)} = \{0, 1, \dots, r\} \quad (3)$$

where $P_{L_{B(x)}(y)}$ is the set of possible routes from the input point of the branch $B(x)$ and the lane $L_{B(x)}(y)$ to every possible output point in the intersection. These possible routes are labeled using an integer number from 0 to r , where 0 represents the absence of a vehicle.

P 's size may vary depending on the total number of branches in the intersection, the number of lanes in each branch, and the possible turn restrictions in each case. These variables add complexity to the problem. The methodology used in OCP to obtain the P sets is based on determining the routes with less possible conflicts between them. This methodology allows the generation of a limited set of routes, selecting just one option for each input point. As a drawback, it introduces a limitation on the number of vehicles that can continue to a destination. In contrast, in OCP-MP we propose that each vehicle can go from any input point to any output branch, adding just one restriction: that in their route they change their way just once. This restriction is added

because any change in the trajectory means that the vehicle must adjust and reduce its velocity. By limiting the trajectory changes to the minimum, it is possible to maintain a constant velocity in the intersection.

Following the intersection example shown in Figure 2, we have an intersection with the same number of lanes in each branch. This means that it is possible to determine the set of paths for only one branch and then translate the values to the other three branches. In Figure 3 we show the paths calculated for the example. Starting from a given branch, the possible paths to the rest of branches are shown in Figure 3.a, Figure 3.b, and Figure 3.c, each one with origin in a specific lane of the input branch. Considering the restriction of performing at most one change in the path trajectory, values 1, 2 and 3 represent the turn to the right of a vehicle. Value 4 represents going straight ahead, and values 5, 6 and 7 points out that the vehicle turns to its left. Therefore, $L_{B(x)}(y) = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7\}$. This set of identifiers will be the same for any origin and destination, because of the symmetry characteristics of the example intersection, although the routes will be different depending on the origin point i_{BL} .

Using these definitions, it is possible to determine that the chromosome of an individual in the genetic algorithm is encoded with as many genes as virtual cells are defined in each input lane of the intersection. That is, given a pattern length of l_p , the size of an individual is calculated as shown in (4).

$$I_l = \sum_{i=1}^n m_i \cdot l_p \quad (4)$$

where m_i is the number of input lanes in each i branch of the intersection.

In Figure 4 we show a representation of the proposed codification where each position of a gene in the chromosome represents a virtual cell of a lane and branch. The value or genotype of each gene is contained in the set $P_{L_{B(x)}(y)}$ of the branch/lane represented depending on the position. The phenotype of each gene is the route followed by a given vehicle in the intersection.

FIGURE 4. Traffic coordination problem encoding for a genetic algorithm.

To guarantee the correct synchronization of every vehicle accessing the intersection, the size of the pattern is equal for every input lane. The set of values $P_{L_{B(x)}(y)}$ might vary depending on the number of possible path combinations in each case.

C. FITNESS FUNCTION

The proposed optimization process has the goal of generating the set of vehicle input patterns for an intersection that guarantees the requirements of the system. This requirement is that, under a given vehicle arrival rate from a specific branch of the intersection, it is possible to route all vehicles to their destination without any collision.

The proposed system, additionally to the intersection descriptive data, receives as input parameter a set of “desirable” flows for each one of the intersection inputs $q_{from}(to)$, where “from” denotes the input branch and “to” is the destination branch for that flow. Equation (5) defines this data structure.

$$Q = [q_1(n), \dots, q_1(3), q_1(2), \dots, q_n(1)] \quad (5)$$

where $Q(i)$ is the i -th element of the Q array (for instance, $Q(1) = q_1(n)$). Each one of these proportions is defined over the maximum capacity of vehicles that can access to the intersection from a specific branch, and therefore, they must comply with the restriction that their sum is lower than or equal to 1. Assuming that a vehicle cannot enter and exit an intersection through the same branch, the number of elements of the array Q will be $n \cdot (n - 1)$.

The fitness function implemented in our proposal uses the microscopic traffic simulator based on the cellular automata described in section II. This simulator allows us, from the

patterns generated for each individual in the population, to reproduce the behavior of the vehicles when crossing the intersection and to count the number of collisions that would have happened. Besides, the function evaluates the similarity between the flows obtained for each population and the desired flows. When the simulation ends, we obtain the following parameters:

- **Average Collisions (C_{avg}):** In each simulation step i , the number of vehicles occupying the same cell (that is, the collisions c_i) are stored. When the simulation steps l_{sim} is over, the average collision score is calculated as the division between the total number of collisions and the number of simulation steps executed.

$$C_{avg} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{l_{sim}} c_i}{l_{sim}} \quad (6)$$

- **Sum of Absolute Errors (SAE):** When the simulation is finished, the input flows Q are compared with those obtained from the optimizer Q_{opt} . The sum of the absolute value of each one of the sub-flows is defined as the value SAE .

$$SAE = \sum_{i=1}^{size(Q)} |Q(i) - Q_{opt}(i)| \quad (7)$$

- **Normalized Mean Absolute Error by flows ($NMAE_{flows}$):** This parameter measures the difference between Q and Q_{opt} , evaluating each sub-flow separately. Each sub-flow is evaluated regarding the difference between the desired flow and the flow obtained from the optimization process.

$$NMAE_{flows} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{size(Q)} \frac{|Q(i) - Q_{opt}(i)|}{Q(i)}}{size(Q)} \quad (8)$$

Taking these metrics into account, the goal of the optimization process is to minimize the result of the fitness function, which means getting the minimum difference between Q and Q_{opt} . We can give different weights to C_{avg} , SAE and $NMAE_{flows}$, in order to achieve solutions where the focus is on obtaining the minimum global difference or obtaining solutions where the minimum difference for each turn option considered independently is guaranteed. Therefore, the fitness function can be expressed as:

$$f = \alpha \cdot C_{avg} + \beta \cdot SAE + \gamma \cdot NMAE_{flows} \quad (9)$$

where α , β and γ are the weights associated with each one of the aforementioned metrics. Each of these weights can be used for different purposes. The α value is used for obtaining valid solutions without collisions. The parameters β and γ allow changing the optimization goals. If the results sought are based on minimizing the total difference between all traffic flow rates, the weight of β will be predominant. Conversely, if the global goal is that each traffic flow rate that composes the Q array has the same importance, γ will be greater than β .

D. GENERATION OF THE INITIAL POPULATION

The convergence, performance, and effectiveness of a genetic algorithm are factors which are highly affected by the definition of the initial population as indicated in [26], [27]. It is quite common to perform a random selection of the genes composing the initial population, but in multiple restriction environments it is necessary to guarantee that the restrictions are met in this population and that there is enough diversity between individuals for the correct convergence of the GA.

To define a function for the generation of initial populations, in our scenario we must consider the following restrictions:

- The length of each individual depends on the number of branches $B(x)$ and lanes $L_{B(x)}$ composing the intersection (defined in (1) and (2), respectively), and also on the number of cells composing the virtual lane l_p .
- The possible values for each gene must be elements of the set $P_{L_{B(x)}(y)}$.

Taking these restrictions into account, the generation process for the initial population follows these steps:

- 1) The function receives as parameters the number of branches and lanes of the intersection, the minimum and maximum length of l_p , the number of individuals of the maximum pattern length to generate, and the set of flows (turn options) to be searched in the optimization process.
- 2) The population size depends on the interval between the minimum and maximum value of the pattern l_p , and on the number of individuals of maximum size received as the input parameter. The number of individuals of each length is obtained in the following way:
 - The minimum pattern length is $\min(l_p)$, the maximum pattern length is $\max(l_p)$ and maximum of individuals with $\max(l_p)$ length is $\max(\text{sub}P)$.
 - The array of pattern lengths is:
 $L = [\min(l_p), \min(l_p) + 1, \dots, \max(l_p)]$
 where the size of L is $\max(l_p) - \min(l_p) + 1$.
 - The size of the set of individuals for the $\min(l_p)$ pattern length is $\max(\text{sub}P)/3$. This value has been obtained empirically to balance the subpopulation sizes and the total size of the final population.
 - The array of subpopulation sizes is:
 $\text{sub}P = [\max(\text{sub}P)/3, (\max(\text{sub}P)/3) + \text{inc}, \dots]$
 where $\text{inc} = \frac{\max(\text{sub}P) - \frac{\max(\text{sub}P)}{3}}{\max(l_p) - \min(l_p)}$
- 3) Considering the expected flows, an array containing the occurrence probabilities for each value in the $P_{L_{B(x)}(y)}$ set is generated.
- 4) Each gene of each individual is set by assigning the values of $P_{L_{B(x)}(y)}$, taking into account the probabilities calculated in the previous step. Each individual will be of the length calculated in step 2.

E. SELECTION OPERATOR

The selection operator used is the function named *selectionremainder* included in the *global optimization* toolbox

of Matlab R2018b. This operator is based on getting an expectations array using the fitness values obtained for each individual in the current population. The parents are selected in a deterministic way, based on the integer part of each value from the expectations array. Once this process is finished, if there are still parents to select, the decimal part of the expectation values is used to stochastically select them [28].

F. CROSSOVER OPERATOR

There are multiple techniques for the crossover function, such as the selection of a single crossover point, the selection of multiple crossover points, or the gene-by-gene combination [29]. Given that our problem requires performing an intensive search in the solution space, we have selected the gene-by-gene combination option, adapting it to the specific proposed codification of the problem. To guarantee the fulfillment of the restrictions, the crossover will be performed pattern-by-pattern. That is, it will be the combination of sets of adjacent genes representing the vehicle pattern in a given branch and lane. The crossover process for variable-length chromosome (OCP-MP-VL) is as follows (see Figure 5):

- 1) The two selected individuals (*parentA* and *parentB*) are divided into the same number of subsets. This number is obtained by multiplying the number of branches in the intersection with the number of lanes composing each branch.
- 2) A new child individual is generated copying the genes and length of *parent B*. The relationship between the two parents lengths is noted as M and is shown in (10).

$$M = \frac{l_p(\text{parent}B)}{l_p(\text{parent}A)} \quad (10)$$

- 3) The fragments generated in step 1 are simultaneously evaluated for *parent A* and *parent B*. With a probability of 0.5, the process decides if each fragment of the child stays as the value corresponding to *parent B* or is substituted with the value of the equivalent fragment from *parent A*. In this last case:
 - a) If $l_p(\text{parent}A) = l_p(\text{parent}B)$, the genes of the fragment are directly substituted (Figure 5.a).
 - b) If $l_p(\text{parent}A) > l_p(\text{parent}B)$, a contraction process must be carried out for the fragment (Figure 5.b).
 - c) If $l_p(\text{parent}A) < l_p(\text{parent}B)$, an expansion process must be carried out for the fragment (Figure 5.c and Figure 5.d).
- 4) The process ends when all the fragments have been evaluated.

The contraction process selects M genes from parent A to obtain a gene from parent B (Figure 5.b). If the M genes of parent A have the same value, this value is assigned to the gene of parent B. When the M genes have different values, but the paths that represent these values have the same destination, the gene of parent B is chosen randomly between the M genes of parent A. Finally, if the M genes from parent A

FIGURE 5. Crossover operator description. a) Crossing points, b) contraction method, c) expansion method if M is an integer value, d) expansion method if M is a decimal value including padding options.

are different among themselves and their phenotype represent paths with different destinations, one of the M genes values is selected and used in parent B. This selection will take into account the proportion of appearance for each value in the parent A chromosome.

On the other hand, for the expansion process, if the size of one fragment is a multiple of the other (M is an integer value), it is possible to carry out a direct correspondence (Figure 5.c). When this is not the case, for the expansion process we need to add padding genes to achieve the needed size. Two different strategies have been defined to add the padding genes: adding zeros or adding values depending on the values of the adjacent genes. In the first case, the advantage is that the added zeros will not generate new collisions in the simulation scenario,

but they present the problem of adding a slight deviation from the original phenotype. In the second case, the isolated behavior of the fragment is maintained, but the new genes might introduce new collisions during the simulation with a higher probability. This process for padding empty genes is shown in Figure 5.d.

G. MUTATION OPERATOR

The mutation operator receives as parameters the genes composing an individual, the mutation rate which indicates the proportion of genes which could be mutated, and the possible values of variation for each gene. This last parameter guarantees the validity of the mutated individual.

Each gene mutates with probability equal to the mutation rate, selecting randomly a value from the possible values regarding its position (possible values of $P_{L_{B(v)}(y)}$ depending on the branch and lane that represents the gene). The mutation process is executed for a number of individuals once the elite population has been stored and the rest of individuals have been part of the crossover process.

For a number of the first generations, the mutation operator is not applied in order to favor a faster convergence to a sub-optimal solution, given the diversity of the initial population defined in section III-D.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

To test and validate the behavior of the proposal, we have conducted a series of experiments. The sets of input data for each experiment have been selected in order to obtain diversity to validate our proposal in different traffic circumstances.

A. EVALUATION METRICS

In each experiment, we have selected the following metrics to evaluate the results:

- **Fitness score:** Value of the fitness function used for the optimization process. This function was described in section III-C and its values represent the weighted sum shown in (9). The best possible value is 0.
- **Computation time:** Measured in seconds, is the time that the optimizer takes to return a solution.
- **Sum of Absolute Errors:** Value representing the difference between the flows or turn options for each input of the intersection obtained in the solution and the values requested at the input of the optimizer. The best possible value is 0.
- **Collisions:** Sum of the collisions between vehicles (that is, coincidences of two or more vehicles in the same cell during a simulation step) produced in each simulation step, divided by the total simulation steps. Any value different from 0 is considered an invalid solution.

B. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The solution proposed in section III allows us to obtain the vehicle arrival patterns for each input point in an intersection

FIGURE 6. Solutions to the same problem using different optimization processes. a) OCP optimizer, b) proposal optimizer (OCP-MP).

that is minimizing the distance to the specific requirements of the system. Figure 6 shows the resolution of an example case using OCP and OCP-MP. In this case, the turning preferences of the vehicles are 3/9 turn right, 2/9 go straight and 1/9 turn left. OCP defines a set of fixed paths and all vehicles with the same input point follow the same path (Figure 6.a). On the other hand, OCP-MP allows using different paths from different input points to the intersection (Figure 6.b).

To evaluate the OCP-MP and OCP-MP-VL optimization processes, we have defined two sets of experiments. The first one is composed of values of input flows for which a candidate solution is already known. In the second set, 100 random flows following a specific distribution have been generated. Besides OCP-MP and OCP-MP-VL, two other known optimizers have been tested with the same input data: Hill Climber (HC) optimization algorithm [27], [30] and OCP as defined in [20].

In section III-F we defined two possible crossover operators depending on how the expansion and contraction processes were implemented. In the first set of experiments, we have tested the results obtained for each possible crossover operator. In the second set, however, we have just used the crossover operator producing the best results. The parameters used for the OCP-MP-VL optimizer are the following:

- **Fitness function:** Based on (9), we have decided to favor the global goal of obtaining the smallest possible difference between Q and Q_{opt} , establishing $\alpha = 0.5$, $\beta = 0.5$ y $\gamma = 0$.
- **Initial population:** We have established that $min(l_p) = 3$, $max(l_p) = 13$, which generates a population of 462 individuals.
- **Mutation operator:** The operator starts acting after the 10 first generations and the mutation rate parameter is set to 0.05.

The selection of these parameters is based on the sensitivity analysis shown in appendix A.

C. EXPERIMENTS DEFINED

For the first set of experiments (input data with known solution) we have defined the following three possible input data:

- **Experiment A1:** Every vehicle wants to turn to the right when arriving the intersection. The input value for the optimizer is:

$$Q_{A1} = [1, 0, 0; 1, 0, 0; 1, 0, 0; 1, 0, 0]$$

- **Experiment A2:** A third part of the vehicles want to turn to the right from each input point and 2/3 want to continue straight in two ways situated one in front of the other, so:

$$Q_{A2} = \left[\begin{matrix} 1 & 2 & 1 \\ \frac{1}{3} & \frac{2}{3} & 0 \end{matrix}; \begin{matrix} 1 & 2 \\ \frac{1}{3} & \frac{2}{3} \end{matrix}, 0 \right]$$

- **Experiment A3:** The third combination of flow values corresponds with the solution obtained for this type of intersection with 4 branches and 3 lanes/branch shown in [31]. This solution is described by the following input flows:

$$Q_{A3} = \left[\begin{matrix} 5 & 2 & 1 & 5 & 2 & 1 \\ \frac{5}{15} & \frac{2}{15} & \frac{1}{15} & \frac{5}{15} & \frac{2}{15} & \frac{1}{15} \end{matrix}; \begin{matrix} 5 & 2 & 1 \\ \frac{5}{15} & \frac{2}{15} & \frac{1}{15} \end{matrix}, \begin{matrix} 5 & 2 & 1 \\ \frac{5}{15} & \frac{2}{15} & \frac{1}{15} \end{matrix} \right]$$

The graphical representation of the solutions for these values of Q_{Ax} is shown in Figure 7.

The second set of experiments (random input preferences) have been carried out for the use case intersection (UCI) with 4 branches and 3 lanes per branch. Because of this, Q has 12 elements. Each branch has been clockwise labeled with the values of 1 to 4 so when applying (5), the following values for Q are obtained:

$$Q_{UCI} = [q_1(4), q_1(3), q_1(2); q_2(1), q_2(4), q_2(3); q_3(2), q_3(1), q_3(4); q_4(3), q_4(2), q_4(1)]$$

In this scenario, there are three turning options: right, go straight and left, where:

$$\begin{aligned} q_{right} &= [q_1(4), q_2(1), q_3(2), q_4(3)] \\ q_{go} &= [q_1(3), q_2(4), q_3(1), q_4(2)] \\ q_{left} &= [q_1(2), q_2(3), q_3(2), q_4(1)] \end{aligned}$$

To count with more extensive testing for our proposal, we have defined three sets of testing data composed each of 100 input flows following these distributions:

- **Experiment B1:** Each set of input flows for a given branch in the intersection is generated following these steps:

- We generate a random value q_{rand1} such that: $0 < q_{rand1} \leq 0.6$.
- We generate a random value q_{rand2} such that: $0 < q_{rand2} \leq 1 - q_{rand1}$.
- We generate a random value q_{rand3} such that: $0 < q_{rand3} \leq 1 - q_{rand1} - q_{rand2}$.

FIGURE 7. Pattern complying with the input requirements of the experiments Ax. The cell values represent the following options: No vehicle (0), vehicle turns right (1, 2, or 3), vehicle goes straight (4), and vehicle turns left (5, 6, or 7). a) Possible solution for Q_{A1} , b) Possible solution for Q_{A2} , and c) Possible solution for Q_{A3} .

- q_{rand1} , q_{rand2} and q_{rand3} are assigned randomly to $q_{right}(i)$, $q_{go}(i)$ and $q_{left}(i)$.
- The process finishes when all values of q_{UCI} have been filled.
- **Experiment B2:** Following the process described for the previous experiment, we generate random flow rates following the proportions of 0.7, 0.2 and 0.1 for each

TABLE 1. Results obtained for the experiments A1, A2 and A3 using the four defined optimization processes.

Value	Optimizer	Crossover type	Experiment A1	Experiment A2	Experiment A3
Fitness score	HC	-	1.3387	0.6356	0.1223
	OCP	-	0.1197	0.0438	0
	OCP-MP	-	0	0	0.0417
	OCP-MP-VL	Zeros	0.0694	0.0556	0
	OCP-MP-VL	No zeros	0	0	0.0417
Computation time (s)	HC	-	466.5469	285.9582	234.9061
	OCP	-	2763.1273	3148.6648	2812.8252
	OCP-MP	-	1841.2997	1459.9598	1737.867
	OCP-MP-VL	Zeros	615.7362	310.6485	1585.902
	OCP-MP-VL	No zeros	306.1409	118.2788	283.3829
Sum of Absolute Errors	HC	-	0	0.0972	0.0586
	OCP	-	0.2393	0.0876	0
	OCP-MP	-	0	0	0.0833
	OCP-MP-VL	Zeros	0.1389	0.1111	0
	OCP-MP-VL	No zeros	0	0	0.0833
Collisions	HC	-	83	27	8
	OCP	-	0	0	0
	OCP-MP	-	0	0	0
	OCP-MP-VL	Zeros	0	0	0
	OCP-MP-VL	No zeros	0	0	0

possible turn direction. The calculated values are also shuffled to assign randomly the specific turn option. The total sum of all the turn options from a given branch will be equal or below 1.

- **Experiment B3:** Finally, in this experiment, we add an extreme case in which the vehicles only want to use a specific turn option. In this case, we assign a random value between 0 and 1 to a turn option between the three available in each branch.

D. EXPERIMENTS RESULTS

The HC, OCP, OCP-MP, and OCP-MP-VL optimizers have been run in each experiment. Of these, the first two, HC and OCP, allow obtaining reference results using known optimizers. The improvements proposed in this work are included in both the OCP-ML and OCP-ML-VL optimizers, but while the first uses a fixed pattern length, the second uses the proposed variable-length chromosome GA to solve the problem.

In Table 1 we show the results obtained when executing each optimizer on each set of flows in experiments A1, A2, and A3. The results of experiments B1, B2, and B3 are shown in Table 2. In this second set of results, given that there is more than one testing value for each experiment, the results show the average value for each case and the corresponding standard deviation (average \pm standard deviation).

V. DISCUSSION

The experiments A1, A2, and A3 defined in section IV-D are based on vehicles preferences with a known solution, which means that *a priori*, we know that it would be possible to obtain a 0 result for the fitness function value and also in the total difference measured at the end of the optimization process. This result is an optimal solution for the problem, and therefore, the optimizers would have achieved

TABLE 2. Results obtained for the experiments B1, B2 and B3, using the four defined optimization processes.

Value	Optimizer	Experiment B1	Experiment B2	Experiment B3
Fitness score	HC	1.169 ± 0.209	0.6278 ± 0.1572	0.5433 ± 0.2456
	OCP	0.0642 ± 0.0057	0.1186 ± 0.0138	0.1746 ± 0.0282
	OCP-MP	0.0649 ± 0.0031	0.1126 ± 0.0390	0.1536 ± 0.0867
	OCP-MP-VL	0.0683 ± 0.008	0.1072 ± 0.013	0.1312 ± 0.0199
Computation time (s)	HC	375.2 ± 7.402	320.6 ± 23.83	326.8 ± 44.83
	OCP	3022 ± 135.5	2992 ± 358	3104 ± 295.1
	OCP-MP	1426.57 ± 134.8	1208.89 ± 114.39	1064.5 ± 175.49
Sum of Absolute Errors	OCP-MP-VL	496.3 ± 207.01	886.6 ± 433.7	389.1 ± 301.8
	HC	0.1628 ± 0.0376	0.2133 ± 0.0257	0.273 ± 0.039
	OCP	0.1283 ± 0.0113	0.2371 ± 0.0275	0.3491 ± 0.0565
	OCP-MP	0.1298 ± 0.0061	0.2253 ± 0.078	0.3072 ± 0.1734
Collisions	OCP-MP-VL	0.1366 ± 0.016	0.2144 ± 0.0259	0.2625 ± 0.0397
	HC	70.14 ± 26.51	38.95 ± 12.86	29.58 ± 22.9
	OCP	0	0	0
	OCP-MP	0	0	0
	OCP-MP-VL	0	0	0

input patterns which comply with the restrictions defined in the desired input flows, while maintaining the simulations collision-free. As shown in Table 1, the only optimizers able to reach this goal are those proposed in this article, the OCP-MP and OCP-MP-VL optimizers. These optimizers achieve a result of $f = 0$ for experiments A1 and A2 when using the crossover function based on adding non-zero values in the expansion operations, and it also achieves a result of $f = 0$ for experiment A3 using the crossover function that adds zeros when expanding the individual during the crossover process. These results are explained because in A1 and A2 one or more branches use the maximum vehicle capacity that they can process (adding zeros to the individuals in the crossover process to pad the individual size generates sub-optimal solutions, given that the optimal solution would require that the individual had every gene with non-zero values). On the other hand, in experiment A3, when it is required to route traffic to any branch and there is no requirement to use the 100% of the capacity of any branch, the crossover with the zero-padding based expansion offers better results, as a zero value guarantees that there are no collisions in that position. OCP-MP and OCP-MP-VL optimizers obtain the same fitness score, but the second one finished in lower computing time. OCP-MP-VL is up to 12 times faster in some cases.

The results obtained with OCP can be seen as acceptable regarding the fitness values, but they are limited by the use of fixed paths. This restriction determines the maximum traffic capacity that can be routed towards each output point of the intersection. Besides, the computation times are much higher than in the rest of the optimizers, because it must solve the problem for each pattern length to be tested as the optimal lengths are not known *a priori*.

Finally, the values obtained for HC are the worst among the compared optimizers. This algorithm can converge in very short computation time, but the solutions returned are far from the optimal solution. Moreover, in every experiment,

FIGURE 8. Average fitness scores (blue bars with circles) and computation times (orange bars with lines) of all the experiments. The value of each bar shows the average value of each optimizer. With a black vertical line on each bar, the standard deviation of the samples is represented.

the results present collisions, and therefore, cannot be considered valid solutions.

In a similar way to the previous experiments, the results obtained by the experiments B1, B2, and B3 (random input preferences) using HC present the lowest computation times, but with the fitness scores farther from the optimal solutions. It is possible to notice that in this case, none of the optimizers can reach the value $f = 0$. This is the expected result, as the input flows have been selected randomly, and therefore the optimizers can only offer a solution as close as possible as the requested, without adding collisions to the simulation. The computation times of OCP-MP and OCP-MP-VL are 2.5 and 8 times lower than the times measured for OCP, respectively. This result, and fitness values very close (B1) or lower (B2 and B3) than the results of the OCP optimizer, show the advantages of using our proposed solution, which can calculate both the optimal vehicle combination and the best pattern size in a single process.

The results of all the experiments have been grouped to obtain the average and standard deviations values of the fitness scores and the computation times of each optimizer. These values are shown in Figure 8.

This summary allows the overall evaluation of the results obtained. OCP-MP and OCP-MP-VL achieve the best fitness scores, getting optimal or quasi-optimal solutions. In addition, the values in the figure show the improvement, in terms of reduction in computation time, of using the optimized with variable-length chromosome versus fixed-length chromosome. The small difference between the average fitness scores obtained with OCP-MP versus OCP-MP-VL is due to OCP-MP optimizer finishing upon reaching the maximum number of generations in some cases, before getting the best solution.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have presented a new methodology to obtain patterns which induce vehicle arrival rates enabling

safe crossings at the intersection while respecting destination preferences.

The proposed methods generalize our previous work by allowing the vehicles to have freedom of path choice in an intersection. This advantage, however, increases the problem complexity, as now the number of possible combinations depends directly on the turn options in each intersection. To mitigate this drawback, we have improved the GA performance by designing, implementing and testing custom crossover and mutation operators adapted to this scenario. Moreover, we have designed a novel methodology for the generation of initial populations based on the searched solutions that preserve the necessary randomness in these algorithms. Given that the pattern length of the solution is not known *a priori*, we have introduced the use of variable-length chromosomes to obtain, at the same time, the best possible fitness score and the shortest pattern length. To achieve this, we have proposed techniques for the expansion and contraction of the chromosome's genes.

After evaluating the optimizers both with known solutions and random data, the results demonstrate the viability of the OCP-MP and OCP-MP-VL optimizers. The second version of our proposal is the optimizer process which achieves the best solutions with the lowest computation times. In addition, the comparison between the obtained results using the proposed system and other solutions such as OCP or widely used algorithms like Hill Climber has concluded that our system can show improvements of up to a 9.1% and computation times 126% lower in average, which proves the advantages of the work.

Although the results of this paper show an improvement from previous solutions in this field, there are certain limitations in the optimization system that should be highlighted. The optimization process is applied to a single intersection, the set of trajectories or paths in the intersection cannot vary from those set at the beginning of process, and the proposed techniques are adapted specifically to the vehicle coordination problem in intersections. Following these statements, we can clearly establish three possible work lines. The first one would be extending this methodology to patterns generated between two or more intersections considering as goal obtaining the minimum vehicle position changes (between lanes) to adapt them to the optimal patterns. The second one would be using the new crossover operator to solve other problems in which it would be useful to codify variable-length population. Finally, we would like to explore the possibility of adapting the proposed system to invalidate the individuals that generate collisions. In this case, if the optimization process cannot be completed due to time restrictions, we can still get a pseudo-optimal solution.

APPENDIX A PARAMETER SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

In order to calibrate the optimization process based on the GA, we have carried out a sensitivity analysis for the main parameters of the algorithm. In Figures 9, 10, and 11 we show the results corresponding to the experiments performed

FIGURE 9. Average values for fitness scores (a) and computation times (b) when evaluating the population size.

FIGURE 10. Average values for fitness scores (a) and computation times (b) when evaluating the crossover probability.

over the population size, the crossover probability, and the mutation probability.

FIGURE 11. Average values for fitness scores (a) and computation times (b) when evaluating the mutation probability.

For each one of the parameters we have randomly selected 10 Q values extracted from the data defined in experiments B1, B2 and B3 described in section IV-C. Using this set of ten values we have executed the optimization process selecting fixed values for two parameters and varying the third one in the following way:

- **Population size:** The initial population of the GA is defined by the size of the set of individuals with the maximum pattern length, as explained in section III-D. The values used for the crossover probability and mutation probability are 0.8 and 0.05 respectively. The size of the set of individuals with maximum pattern has been changed from 32 to 100.
- **Crossover:** The crossover probability has been changed in each optimization process between 0.7 and 0.99. We have selected 64 as the number of initial individuals with maximum pattern length (which generates a population of 462 individuals), and a mutation probability of 0.05.
- **Mutation:** The mutation probability has been changed in each optimization process between 0.01 and 0.2. We have selected 64 as the number of initial individuals with maximum pattern length (which generates a population of 462 individuals), and a crossover probability of 0.8.

Once all experiments have been carried out, we have calculated the average values for fitness scores and computation times. Regarding the population size, in

Figures 9.a and 9.b it is shown how above 60, the fitness score remains stable. On the other hand, there is a local minimum for a value of 64 in computation times. Due to these results, we have selected 64 as the input parameter which generates an initial population of 462 individuals.

Evaluating in a similar way the results shown in Figures 10 and 11, we can establish that the optimal values for crossover and mutation probabilities are 0.8 and 0.05 respectively.

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include intelligent agents, the IoT architectures, and intelligent transportation systems.

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